

METHODS OF SPEECH SKILLS FORMATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH

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Abstract: The article gives opinions and recommendations on the formation of speech skills in children based on the use of methods of speech development of children of junior school age. These recommendations can be used by pedagogues in the school education system.

Keywords. Imitation, communication, direction, practical activity, intellect, environment, education, development.

INTRODUCTION. Speech development of children of primary school age is a complex pedagogical and psychological process, which does not consist only in imitating the speech heard by the child. This process is related to the development of communication activities in children and, first of all, the need for communication. The child's orientation to new aspects of existence - the transition from practical activities to studying the world, and then people, their relationships, creates the need for new means of communication that serve new purposes. Expanding the child's lexicon allows him to master a wider and more diverse expression of his experiences. For the modern and full development of speech, interaction with the people around him is necessary to enrich the content of the child's need for communication. The reason for children's acquisition of speech is that the basis of their communicative activities is the organization of need-motivation, and its composition has changed. In the verbal stage, the child develops slow speech. The main importance of the period leading up to this stage

is that it creates the conditions necessary to move to the next stage - the stage of the emergence of active speech. In the second stage of the child's acquisition of active speech, three main aspects are distinguished: emotional relations; relations during joint activity (cooperation), sound and light relations. Each considered aspect of the child's communication with adults helps him to accept the communicative task set before him by adults, which requires the use of words as a conditionally accepted tool for mutual understanding in society. In addition, each considered aspect of the communicative factor to one degree or another and in its own way helps children to solve the communicative task, that is, to use speech. At the third stage of speech development, its material (vocabulary and grammar) is inextricably linked to the child's need for communication with adults and its content, changing the task of communication. This leads to the acquisition of new, more complex and comprehensive aspects of the child's speech. The fact that speech occupies a decisive place in the mental formation of a child increases the importance of the conditions and factors that support its development at various stages. The issue of the driving forces of the development of speech is of particular importance due to their intense and spontaneous implementation. Determining the forces that stimulate or slow down the development of children's speech is the key to organizing pedagogical efforts in this process with clear goals.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

"Truly, language and thought cannot live without each other," writes A. M. Borodich - Although language and thinking cannot live without each other, they do not represent the same phenomenon. Thought is the end of objective existence, and language is a means of conveying and strengthening thoughts to other people. It is known that the development of the speech of school-aged children is carried out in various types of activities: in the activities of

familiarization with natural objects; in teaching literacy; in game activity; in the performance of various works in the process of socially useful work. However, as shown by A.M. Borodich, F.A. Sokhin, Ye.I. Tikheeva, O.S. Ushakova, A.P. Usova, A.P.

Fedorenko and other researchers, the development of speech occurs in specially planned and organized activities. its implementation is desirable in all respects. At the same time, in order to achieve the best results in the organization of activities, it is necessary to comply with the following requirements: planning activities taking into account their purpose, content and duration of implementation; clearly defining the independent activities of children in the activities of solving speech tasks of an analytical-synthetic nature, establishing connections between subjects, distinguishing similarities; clearly defining the content of the activity, time and method of solving specific issues of an educational nature; arousing children's interest in speech formation activities; maintaining consistency between planned activities. It is known that the tradition of using signs in speech is not controlled by anyone. It is necessary to remember and use the established tradition. Therefore, in order to acquire speech, it is necessary to know the tradition of using language signs (their combinations, their interchangeability. In this regard, one of the researchers, L.P. Fedorenkova, G.A. Fomichevalar, puts forward a methodologically important idea: "Get the child to speak to teach, they write, to make it easier to understand the meaning of language material (training the organs of speech), language signs, lexical-grammatical signs (training the intellect), to teach him to express the appreciation of existence using lexical-grammatical signs (training respect and feelings) , it means to help to facilitate the remembering of literary standards". Agreeing with a reasonable approach to the acquisition of speech by a child, we draw our attention to the fact that the authors of this manual often use "help", "training" and other expressions -he, but they pay little attention to how to help and practice. In order

to prepare the child for successful studies at school, it is necessary to create appropriate conditions for him to acquire all the riches of his native language.

DISCUSSIONS

It is necessary to implement the development of children's speech on the basis of an appropriate program. In this program, the range of knowledge about the environment and the size of the vocabulary, speech skills and abilities that should be formed in children at each age stage are determined, and it should provide for the education of certain qualities of this person (approachability, politeness, health, modesty). The speech development program is based on scientific principles and is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's personality. The speech development program is implemented in the educational, play, work and household activities of the child.

In the conditions of public education, it is considered the leading means of forming children's speech. Teaching the mother tongue is a process of planning and purposeful development of children's cognitive abilities, assimilation of the simplest knowledge about the world and relevant vocabulary, formation of speech skills and abilities. The main form of education of children of preschool age is educational activities. The following types of activities can be distinguished for didactic purposes: • activity of introducing new material; • activities related to strengthening knowledge, skills and abilities; • activities related to generalization and systematization of knowledge; • final activities or audit (control) activities. Activities related to teaching children their mother tongue should be carried out in each group, taking into account the age of the children and the level of speech development of each child. Because the content of knowledge, their composition, the choice of methods and methods, the number of activities held per week, the duration of each activity depends on it. , it is recommended to conduct in the form of stage performances. They should be not only entertaining, but also

educational.

The development of children's speech between 3 and 5 years old should be emotional. In this, exhibitionism, game methods and didactic games are widely used. Activities related to the development of children's speech between the ages of 5 and 7 have a specific task - that is, they are intended to prepare children for studying at school. In educational activities, the pedagogue should develop the ability to carry out educational activities in addition to speech tasks (being attentive, listening to the teacher's task, understanding and clearly performing it, being able to think in front of a group of children, simple evaluation of the answer of a peer can give, etc.) also performs the task. □ In the case of proper education, by the age of seven, a child acquires oral speech and can communicate freely with older relatives and peers; □ takes the initiative in the dialogue and expresses his opinion, knows how to attract the interlocutor's attention, respond to him with words, actions and words; □ express their thoughts in the form of simple sentences and short texts; □ uses different parts of speech, allusions, comparisons and synonyms in expressing opinions; □ begins to show a critical attitude to the speech, tries to correct it grammatically, due to this, word weaving ends, and the number of grammatical errors in the speech decreases; □ pronounces all the sounds in the mother tongue correctly. Many speech communication and skills in children are formed outside of classes. In children's preschool education organizations, communication of children with adults (pedagogues, medical nurses, teaching assistants, etc.) takes place in various types of activities. RESULTS.

During the study activity, the pedagogue forms independent speech activity in them. Children's vocabulary and knowledge acquired in educational activities are strengthened and activated. The participation of the pedagogue in the games helps to enrich the vocabulary and cultivate the culture of speech communication. In the process of organizing construction games, the teacher identifies and

activates a large group of words that are difficult for children (determining the quality, quantity, volume and location of things in space, etc.).

Textual, dynamic musical games, dramatization games help to form the expressiveness of the child's speech, practice the correct pace, breathing, and good diction. In the process of many games, children get acquainted with artistic texts, remember them and begin to use them independently. With the help of didactic games, children's knowledge about the environment is strengthened, vocabulary is strengthened, clarified and activated. Didactic games are used to practice speaking skills (interrupting phrases, changing words, weaving stories, etc.). Household activities create great opportunities for the child to communicate with adults. In order for household activities to serve as a means of speech development, the pedagogue should lead them. In the course of properly organized household activities (eating, dressing, gymnastics, travel, etc.), that is, if the pedagogue, especially in small groups, the pedagogue explains in detail the names of household items, their parts, quality, characteristics, purpose of use, with them Children's vocabulary will be enriched if they perform the appropriate actions and interpret it, if children learn, teach them to use household vocabulary. If the pedagogue uses similes, comparisons, synonyms, folk works (proverbs, proverbs, fairy tales) widely and skillfully in his speech, his speech will be concise and expressive. Children's fiction serves as a powerful tool for the comprehensive development of children, it has a great impact on the development and enrichment of children's speech. Children's books reveal and explain to the child the life of society and nature, the world of human feelings and relationships in poetic images. The artistic word enriches the child's speech, makes it unique, expressive, helps to understand the beauty of mother speech.

CONCLUSION

One of the main tasks of general secondary school pedagogues is to form

the correct oral speech of children as a result of mastering the artistic language of their people. This general task consists of the following special tasks: education of sound culture of speech, enrichment, strengthening and activation of vocabulary, improvement of grammatical correctness of speech, formation of oral (dialogic) speech, development of fluent speech, education of interest in artistic speech, teaching literacy preparation. Conducting teaching activities with children in two forms of oral speech - dialogue and storytelling - will continue to develop their rapid speech. In the process of forming the grammatical system of school-age children's speech, it is necessary to form the skill of performing exercises in correct speech.

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